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PPWSim: Privacy preserving wireless sensor network simulator

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ABSTRACT

The Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) is a monitoring system consisting of a large number of wireless devices forming a multi-hop network without infrastructure. WSN nodes are generally cheap resource-constrained devices detecting environmental features using sensors. Although well-established communication protocols for Internet systems can provide reliable and secure communication between peers, applying similar solutions on WSNs could overwhelm the resource-constrained technology WSNs consist of. Moreover, the broadcast nature of wireless communication could reveal contextual information to external actors eavesdropping on RF signals. Therefore, it is of particular concern to research communication protocols designed explicitly for WSN to preserve network resources and privacy. In this paper, PPWSim is presented, a simulator developed to study a privacy-preserving communication protocol for edge data processing in WSNs. The simulator is based on the simulation environment nsnam NS3; therefore, it can be easily extended or used as a framework for developing other WSN simulators.

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1. Motivation and significance

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) commonly consist of a large number of sensing nodes deployed in a dynamic environment for specific monitoring purposes. Nodes must self-configure and collaborate with other nodes to autonomously form a network without infrastructure where data can flow from sensor nodes to external actors interacting with sink nodes. Sensor nodes are low-cost devices equipped with sensors and constrained in processing,

bandwidth, storage, and energy resources. On the other hand, sink nodes are not severely resource-constrained, and their role is to act as a gateway to external systems requiring data from sensor nodes. However, these particular WSN characteristics of low-cost devices, multi-hop routing, and no infrastructure that shape the versatility of WSNs make them subject to various attacks [1].

The large number of sensor nodes composing a WSN allows very granular monitoring of the environment; nonetheless, a large number of sensing nodes imply large amounts of data, and data must be processed to extract valuable information. However, typical solutions convey all the sensed data to a central processing point, usually in the cloud. Therefore, missing the opportunity to take advantage of the computing power of nodes

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Fig. 1. The figure displays the onion message and its circuit-like path in the WSN. The onion message path is encoded in the onion head. The onion body carries computer code and a binary string used to store an aggregated value. The computer code executes at sensor nodes in the onion message path, embedding the execution result in the carried binary string.

forming the WSN and overloading the multi-hop network raised by resource-constrained technology. Several privacy-preserving data aggregation solutions emerged [2–5] to preserve privacy against attackers, reduce the communication overhead, and employ sensor node processing capabilities. These solutions work by aggregating sensor readings from multiple nodes along routing paths as data travel toward the sink node. The feasibility, and effectiveness of these solutions are usually tested in simulation environments before deployment. However, even popular network simulators such as NS3 [6] lack a generalized framework for WSN simulations that would serve as a common denominator for reproducibility of research results. In this paper, we present a simulation framework for WSN using NS3. We validate our approach using the framework to implement a general purpose data and query privacy preserving protocol for wireless sensor networks using onion routing [7].

2. Problem overview

PPWSim was developed to study the implementation of the privacy-preserving communication protocol [7] in a WSN and: **(a)** assess the response time, **(b)** conduct a scalability study, **(c)** determine if the network topology significantly affects the protocol performance. The software released with this manuscript is an extended version allowing broader manipulation of the simulation environment for future research.

The communication protocol design is characterized by messages containing a layered object made of several encryption layers similar to the one employed in the Onion Routing [8]. Besides the layered object, messages defined by our protocol also contain a payload. By our protocol design, the payload consists of information related to edge data processing (general-purpose computer code) and a binary string whose purpose is to carry an aggregated value. In the rest of the manuscript, the software, and the documentation, we refer to the *onion head* as the layered object, the *onion body* as the message payload, and the *onion message* as the message consisting of the onion head and the onion body. The onion message is depicted in Fig. 1.

The communication protocol leads computer code and a partial result through WSN nodes, each node in the message path executing the computer code and contributing with its sensed value to the partial result. When the message returns back to the issuer sink node, it contains the required aggregated value computed on sensor readings of nodes specified at message construction.

The simulator implementation differs from the technique presented in [7] by the following aspects: (1) the simulator does not constrain processing time of the onion message at sensor nodes, (2) the simulator forwards padding bytes instead of computer code, (3) onion head layers does not include symmetric encryption keys (the onion message is processed alike on each sensor node in the onion message path).

3. Software description

To pursue research questions raised by the conceptualized privacy-preserving data aggregation protocol, we developed a simulator based on the NS3 [6] simulation environment. The simulator allows the user to manipulate various parameters affecting the traveling time of onion messages. We refer to the traveling time of onion messages as the elapsed time between issuing the onion message from the sink node and the return of the issued onion message to the issuer sink node.

3.1. Software functionalities

This section describes software functionalities and parameters affecting the simulator output. To facilitate the use of the simulator, we implemented the setup of simulation parameters through a configuration file. Moreover, parameters *simulation name*, *simulation seed*, *routing*, *topology*, and *number of nodes in the network* can be set through command-line arguments. An accurate description of the software parameters can be found in the software repository.

The simulator constructs a network consisting of s sensor nodes and one sink node. Sensor nodes are deployed on a plane based on one of the following deployment schemes: the *grid*

topology (GT) and the *random disc topology* (RDT). In the former, sensor nodes are deployed according to a grid structure; each sensor node is equidistant from the closest sensor nodes in cardinal directions. In the latter, sensor nodes are randomly deployed on a disc-shaped plane. The sink node is deployed in the center of the network in both GT and RDT. Both deployment schemes allow the user to maintain the same average node density at diverse values of s .

The wireless communication in the simulated network adheres to the IEEE 802.11n standard for local wireless networks. Our simulator allows the choice between the 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz carrier frequency and various modulation coding schemes [9].

Each node in the WSN has installed the IP protocol, and messages are transmitted over the TCP protocol to ensure a reliable in-order data delivery. Since WSNs are usually characterized by a small Maximum Segment Size (MSS) and Maximum Transmission Unit (MTU) [10], the simulator allows to set these parameters to the required value. Messages are routed using a routing algorithm for multi-hop ad-hoc wireless networks provided by the NS3 environment. We implemented a simplified procedure for the installation of the routing algorithm by setting the specific parameter. The supported routing algorithms for multi-hop ad-hoc wireless networks are: Ad Hoc On-Demand Distance Vector (AODV) [11], Dynamic Source Routing (DSR) [12], Optimized Link State Routing Protocol (OLSR) [13] and Destination-Sequenced Distance Vector (DSDV) [14].

Our simulator implements cryptographic operations using the Libsodium library [15]. Layers of the onion head are encrypted by applying the *Sealed box*, a public-key cryptosystem based on the Curve25519 [16] with the key length of 256b. Therefore, each encryption layer increases the onion head size by 48bytes due to the shared secret.

Onion messages are executing in the WSN as explained in Section 2; moreover, the simulator allows to control the following properties of onion messages:

- *Onion message path length*: number of sensor nodes to include in the onion message path.
- *Uniform onion head size*: the onion head size is maintained uniform by adding padding to the onion head when a layer of the onion head is decrypted.
- *No onion body*: onion messages will not include the onion body.
- *Onion body size*: set the onion body size to emulate the transportation of computer code in the onion body.
- *Data aggregation*: the onion body contains a value, and each sensor node aggregates its sensor reading to the value carried in the onion body.

Due to the high error rate of wireless multi-hop networks and the usually large size of onion messages, we implemented a watchdog timer to interrupt the forwarding of an onion message if it does not reach the next hop within the selected time frame. Furthermore, the watchdog timer will also trigger the issuing of a new onion message having the same properties as the interrupted one.

3.1.1. Simulator output

The simulator output is written on the `STDOUT` and on an output file. An example of the output file content is listed as given in [Box 1](#).

The output file contains a description of the parameters used to run the simulation and four CSV headers. The CSV headers describe the data rows of the output file. In the following paragraph, we describe the data output of the simulation.

The `ONION_DETAILS` rows include the traveling time of onion messages, which is measured from the issuing by the sink node

until the onion message returns to the sink node. `ONION_ROUTING` rows enclose the time an onion message travels from one node in the onion message path to the next node in the onion message path. Both `ONION_DETAILS` and `ONION_ROUTING` include details about the onion message size in bytes and the `onionId` an identifier to uniquely identify an onion message among data rows. `TIMEOUT` rows notify interrupted onion messages. The `NODE_DETAILS` rows report (X,Y) coordinates of nodes able to communicate with the sink node (sensor nodes listed in the `<IP, public-key>` structure, as explained in Section 3.2). Moreover, if OLSR routing is selected, also the node degree is reported. We refer to the node degree as the number of one-hop neighbors of a node.

Besides the mentioned output file, each simulation run additionally produces statistics about the communication traffic generated during the simulation. The communication traffic is measured at MAC and application layers separately. Therefore, allowing to compare the ratio between the data transmitted at the application layer and the total communication overhead generated in the network.

3.2. Illustrative example

The simulator provides a simulation environment for the privacy-preserving data aggregation protocol described in Section 2, allowing the user to adjust parameters described in Section 3.1 by setting a configuration file. The simulator is launched by executing one of the following commands in the NS3 home directory. The second command demonstrates the use of command-line arguments.

```

$ ./waf --run onion-routing-wsn
$ ./waf --run "onion-routing-wsn --a_simNum=0 --a_name=test
--a_routing=olsr --a_topology=grid --a_nodeNumber=10 "

```

At simulator start-up, the configuration file is read, and simulation parameters are set up. Then, the network is constructed according to the selected network topology, and applications are installed on nodes. Since in the RDT, nodes are deployed at random locations in the available disc-shaped space, some nodes might not be able to communicate with the sink node. Therefore, the simulator works in two phases; the first phase is meant to identify sensor nodes reachable by the sink node.

In the first phase, sensor nodes start up sequentially to prevent network congestions, each sensor node sending its public key to the sink node. The sink node holds a list of reachable nodes consisting of pairs `<IP, public-key>`, each entry corresponding to a sensor node able to communicate with the sink node.

In the second phase, the sink node starts constructing an onion message by selecting sensor nodes to include in the onion message path. Sensor nodes are randomly selected from the list of reachable nodes. Onion messages are issued by the sink node sequentially; after an onion message returns at the sink node, the following onion message is issued. Onion messages are processed on sensor nodes conditional to parameters set in the configuration file and mentioned in Section 3.1. The simulator ends when all onion messages specified in the configuration file complete their execution.

3.3. Software architecture

The software architecture is presented using the UML class diagram in [Fig. 2](#) to describe the structure and the UML component diagram in [Fig. 3](#) to show the interaction with NS3 modules. At simulator start-up, the `WsnConstructor` component reads parameters defined in the configuration file using the `ConfigStore` module, creates nodes and network devices using the `Network` module, builds the network topology using the `Mobility` module,

```

-----Simulation description-----
Simulation name: test_OLSR_GRID_10_0
Simulation randomstream setup, run: 1, seed:1
Total sensornodes: 10 and 1 sink node
Wireless: IEEE 802.11n at 2.4GHz, , DataMode: HtMcs1, ControlMode: HtMcs1, MTU:1280, MSS:536
Network topology: GRID with row size: 3.
Distance between nodes on X-axis: 60m. Distance between nodes on Y-axis: 60m. Sink node located at x:60,y:60
Routing: OLSR
Routing setup time: 60s, nodes are starting sequentially with 200ms interval, onion starts at: 67s
Onion path lengths: 5 10 15 repeated each path length 1 times.
Simulation started at: Mon Nov 22 15:14:57 2021
--csv headers--
onion_details,sim_name,sim_num,num_of_nodes,topology,routing,onion_id,packet_size,onion_head_size
,onion_body_size,onion_path_length,sent_at,recv_at,query_time_to_return
onion_routing,sim_name,sim_num,num_of_nodes,topology,routing,onion_id,send_ip,recv_ip,packet_size
,onion_head_size,onion_body_size,sent_at,recv_at,hop_time
timeout,sim_name,sim_num,num_of_nodes,topology,routing,onion_id,onion_path_length,abort_time
node_details,sim_name,sim_num,num_of_nodes,topology,routing,coord_x,coord_y,node_degree
-----Simulation output-----
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,1,10.1.0.1,10.1.0.7,411,267,134,67.800000,67.802884,0.002884
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,1,10.1.0.7,10.1.0.4,411,267,134,67.802884,67.817742,0.014858
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,1,10.1.0.4,10.1.0.9,411,267,134,67.817742,67.835166,0.017424
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,1,10.1.0.9,10.1.0.6,411,267,134,67.835166,67.850985,0.015819
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,1,10.1.0.6,10.1.0.10,411,267,134,67.850985,67.872124,0.021139
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,1,10.1.0.10,10.1.0.1,411,267,134,67.872124,67.873909,0.001785
onion_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,1,411,267,134,5,67.800000,67.873909,0.073909
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,2,10.1.0.1,10.1.0.10,671,527,134,68.373909,68.378262,0.004352
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,2,10.1.0.10,10.1.0.9,671,527,134,68.378262,68.396232,0.017970
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,2,10.1.0.9,10.1.0.11,671,527,134,68.396232,68.413327,0.017095
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,2,10.1.0.11,10.1.0.4,672,528,134,68.413327,68.421543,0.008216
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,2,10.1.0.4,10.1.0.7,672,528,134,68.421543,68.423928,0.002385
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,2,10.1.0.7,10.1.0.5,672,528,134,68.423928,68.444033,0.020105
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,2,10.1.0.5,10.1.0.4,672,528,134,68.444033,68.461734,0.017701
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,2,10.1.0.4,10.1.0.2,672,528,134,68.461734,68.480690,0.018956
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,2,10.1.0.2,10.1.0.5,671,527,134,68.480690,68.497158,0.016468
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,2,10.1.0.5,10.1.0.9,671,527,134,68.497158,68.517373,0.020215
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,2,10.1.0.9,10.1.0.1,671,527,134,68.517373,68.521615,0.004242
onion_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,2,671,527,134,10,68.373909,68.521615,0.147706
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.1,10.1.0.9,931,787,134,69.021615,69.022961,0.001346
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.9,10.1.0.11,931,787,134,69.022961,69.025259,0.002298
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.11,10.1.0.6,931,787,134,69.025259,69.037589,0.012330
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.6,10.1.0.9,932,788,134,69.037589,69.043895,0.006306
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.9,10.1.0.2,932,788,134,69.043895,69.047897,0.004002
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.2,10.1.0.8,932,788,134,69.047897,69.064188,0.016291
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.8,10.1.0.7,932,788,134,69.064188,69.070067,0.005879
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.7,10.1.0.3,932,788,134,69.070067,69.073157,0.003089
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.3,10.1.0.2,932,788,134,69.073157,69.075896,0.002739
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.2,10.1.0.8,932,788,134,69.075896,69.080590,0.004695
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.8,10.1.0.11,932,788,134,69.080590,69.085924,0.005333
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.11,10.1.0.4,932,788,134,69.085924,69.091843,0.005919
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.4,10.1.0.3,932,788,134,69.091843,69.094292,0.002449
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.3,10.1.0.2,931,787,134,69.094292,69.096980,0.002688
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.2,10.1.0.4,931,787,134,69.096980,69.100846,0.003866
onion_routing,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,10.1.0.4,10.1.0.1,931,787,134,69.100846,69.105257,0.004411
onion_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,3,931,787,134,15,69.021615,69.105257,0.083641
node_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,10.1.0.1,60,60,8
node_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,10.1.0.2,0,0,3
node_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,10.1.0.3,60,0,5
node_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,10.1.0.4,120,0,3
node_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,10.1.0.5,0,60,5
node_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,10.1.0.6,60,180,4
node_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,10.1.0.7,120,60,5
node_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,10.1.0.8,0,120,5
node_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,10.1.0.9,60,120,7
node_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,10.1.0.10,120,120,4
node_details,test_OLSR_GRID_10_0,0,10,grid,olsr,10.1.0.11,0,180,3
-----Simulation end: Mon Nov 22 15:15:00 2021-----

```

Box 1.

sets up the wireless communication using the WiFi module, installs the internet stack using the Internet module, sets up routing using the corresponding module, installs and starts applications on nodes using Network and Core modules. The WsnConstructor component creates one instance of classes OUTPUTMANAGER and ONIONVALIDATOR passing them to SensorNode and Sink applications. The OUTPUTMANAGER instance manages the output of the simulation writing on the STDOUT and the output file. The ONIONVALIDATOR instance allows checking if the onion message reached the next-hop node within the watchdog timer.

In the first phase of the simulation, instances of the class SENSORNODE send its public-key to the Sink node by calling Handshake(). When the Sink node receives a handshake message, it registers the sensor node in the m_nodeManager <IP,public-key> structure.

All messages traveling the WSN are constructed with the Protobuf library [17] using the PROTOPACKET class.

In the second phase of the simulation, the instance of the class SINK creates an onion message by calling SelectRoute() and PrepareOnion(). The method SelectRoute() randomly selects sensor nodes to include in the onion message path from the m_nodeManager <IP,public-key> structure. The method PrepareOnion() uses an instance of the class ONIONMANAGER to create the onion head. The ONIONMANAGER class extends the ONIONROUTING class with the implementation of EncryptLayer() and DecryptLayer() using the Libsodium library. The abstract class ONIONROUTING allows onion head creation and layer decryption while omitting the implementation of encryption/decryption functions. The constructed PROTOPACKET instance containing the onion head and the onion body is then sent to a sensor node by calling the function

unreachable for other nodes and unable to participate in the routing.

4. Impact

The PPWSim is in the base a WSN simulator with an added usecase, the data and origin privacy-preserving protocol based on onion routing. Experiments requiring the basic WSN network as well as experiments requiring the additional privacy-preserving characteristics can be simulated on the proposed software.

The WsnConstructor component allows effortless manipulation of generic WSN properties through a configuration file; furthermore, the component is structured in layers corresponding to the ISO/OSI model [18], allowing intuitive extension of functionalities. The Wsn_node component represents a generic WSN node that provides transport layer services, data interchange through Protobuf [17] objects, access to node location information, node deactivation/reactivation, and centralized management of the simulator's output through the OutputManager component. Therefore, the Wsn_node component can be extended to model sensor node or sink node behavior of specific WSN applications, and the Protobuf integration facilitates the development of communication protocols. The ONIONROUTING class provided by the PPWSim is encryption agnostic and can be re-used to develop other simulators using the onion routing technique [8]. Moreover, PPWSim is based on the NS3 simulation environment, allowing further extension with components provided by the NS3. The NS3 provides: error models to simulate noisy channels, PCAP traces useful for studying location privacy protection in WSNs [19], mobility models to simulate specific scenarios requiring the motion of nodes [20], and many other tools.

The authors were not able to find any existing simulation that could be adaptable to special requirements, such as the privacy preservation that was the main goal of the research described in [7].

An important portion of the scientific research needs to be supported by empirical evaluation. New scientific ideas can be simulated in specially developed software, but the implementation time along with the inevitable software production problems can deter scientists from pursuing further research. Simulation environments, such as NS3, help in rapid development of specialized simulation environments. After a thorough research of the available opensource tools, the authors were unable to find a suitable solution for at the time of writing for the data and origin privacy-preserving WSN network simulating environment. The proposed solution is based on an industry leading simulation environment incorporating the proposed properties.

The software has been used on a few projects at the authors' home institutions University of Primorska and Innorenew CoE. The most notable projects were "Intelligent floor" presented in [21] and "Mrakova domačija historical site", presented in [22]. Already published results presented in [23] are based on the presented software simulator.

5. Conclusions

This paper presents PPWSim, a simulator based on the NS3 [6] simulation environment. PPWSim was designed specifically to study the communication protocol presented in [7]. The simulator allows the user to set simulation parameters affecting the traveling time of messages in the network. Besides future investigations on the solution described in [7], the presented software could serve as a framework for developing other simulators in the scope of WSNs or simulators using the onion routing technique [8].

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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